

**THE EFFECT OF WORK SKILLS AND
EMPLOYEE'S JOB INVOLVEMENT ON EMPLOYEE
PERFORMANCE THROUGH JOB SATISFACTION
IN MANPOWER OFFICE OF MEDAN, INDONESIA**

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Abstract:

Bureaucratic reform is a strategic phase to build the state apparatus to become more efficient and effective in carrying out the general tasks of government and national development. The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of work skills and employee's job involvement through job satisfaction. This type of research is causal with a quantitative approach. The population in this study was 62 employees and the sample in this study was the entire population and utilized the saturated sample method. Data was collected by distributing questionnaires to all respondents in this study. The results of the first sub-structural research indicate that work skills affect job satisfaction and job involvement influences job satisfaction. The results of the second sub-structural research indicate that work skills influence employee performance. Job involvement influences employee performance and job satisfaction affects employee performance. The path analysis shows that job satisfaction is not able to mediate between work skills, job involvement and employee performance.

Keywords: work skills, job involvement, job satisfaction, employee performance

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1. Introduction

The development of science and technology and the rapid flow of globalization have conveyed changes and generated new paradigms in the workplace and in the sphere of education. Organizations not only pursue the attainment of high productivity, but also pay more attention to performance in the process of triumphing it. Thus, performance is a key dynamic for every individual and organization in achieving productivity.

There are several outlooks on the subject of the factors which affect employee performance. Stern in Mangkunegara (2013) states that some factors which influence employee performance can include individual factors and organizational environment. Performance is the end result of work that can be accomplished by a person or group of people in an organization in accordance with their respective authorities and responsibilities in order to realize the organizational goals (Sentono, 2014). There is a close relationship between individual performance and organizational performance, in other words, if employee performance is good, organizational performance will also be enhanced. Management is to achieve high human resource performance to improve the company as a whole (Mas'ud, 2014).

Fundamentally, job satisfaction is when each individual have a different level of satisfaction in accordance with the values that apply. This is due to the differences in each of these individuals, the more aspects of work that are in accordance with the aspirations of the individual, the higher the level of satisfaction obtained. It will get a low level of satisfaction if the opposite occurs. Some factors that can affect employee performance are employee work skills that are individual in nature. It is because each individual will have different skill levels depending on their abilities and experience. Work skills have great benefits for individuals, companies and society. For individual, work skills can improve their performance so that they receive compensation according to their achievements (Wahyudi, 2002). Skill is known to be a person's ability to complete the task assigned to him. These skills can also in forms of technical skills, human skills and conceptual skills such as the ability to take advantage of opportunities, accuracy, using equipment owned by the company in achieving its goals (Hasibuan, 2000).

In addition to work skills, job involvement is one of the factors that causes employee performance enhancement. Prasetyo (2016) explains that job involvement is one of the variables that can be used to predict conditions in an organization, such as the level of absenteeism and turnover. This happens because job involvement can indicate the level of integration between employees and their work. If the employee integrates with the work, then the work will be seen as to some degree that is very important, will be more involved and provide more time to do the work. As a result, employees who have high job involvement will be willing to work overtime, hardly ever late, and have a low absence rate.

Employee job involvement is a factor that affects employee performance. Job involvement is also a building strength that dashes almost all aspects of human resources, if not handled properly then employees fail to fully involve. In work, job involvement is

the level of employee identification of their work, actively participating in their work, and considers performance in their work to be more valuable for their own good (Robbins & Coulter, 2010). Job involvement is the level at which a person attaches himself to his work, actively participates in it and considers his performance important for his value (Simanjuntak & Raharja, 2013).

2. Literature Review

2.1 Employee Performance

Etymologically, performance comes from the expression of work performance as stated by Mangkunegara (2013) that the term performance comes from actual performance namely the quality and quantity of work achieved by an employee in carrying out their duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him. Performance is a concept that is universal which include the operational effectiveness of an organization, parts of the organization, and its employees based on predetermined standards and criteria. Employee performance in general is the result achieved by employees in working for a particular job. Furthermore, Robbins (2009) defines performance as a function of the interaction between ability and motivation. Performance will affect how much employees contribute to the company, including output quantity, output quality, output period, workplace attendance and cooperative attitude.

Gibson, Ivancevich and Donnely (2012) suggest that the factors that influence performance are:

- 1) Individual variables, including abilities and skills both physical and mental, background, such as family, social level and experience, demographics, regarding age, origin and gender.
- 2) Psychological variables, including perceptions, attitudes, personality, learning, motivation.
- 3) Organizational variables, including resources, leadership, rewards, structure and job design.

Bernardin and Russel (2010) mention there are six criteria to measure the performance of an employee, namely:

- 1) The ability to produce in accordance with the quality standards set by the company (Quality).
- 2) The ability to produce in accordance with the amount set by the company (Quantity).
- 3) An activity is completed at the desired time by taking into account the coordination of other outputs and the time available for the activity (Timeliness),
- 4) The level of application of human, financial, technological, and material resources that can be optimized (Cost effectiveness).
- 5) The level of an employee to work carefully without the strict supervision of the supervisor (Need of supervision).

- 6) The level of an employee in maintaining self-esteem, good name and cooperation, among coworkers and subordinates (Interpersonal input).

Hasibuan (2012) revealed several goals and uses of employee performance appraisal as follows:

- a) As a basis for making decisions used for promotion, termination and determination of the amount of compensation.
- b) To measure work performance, namely the extent to which employees can succeed in their work.
- c) As a basis for evaluating the effectiveness of all activities in the company.
- d) As a basis for evaluating training programs and the effectiveness of work schedules, work methods, organizational structure, supervision styles, working conditions, and work equipment.
- e) As an indicator to determine the need for training for employees who are in the organization.
- f) As a tool to increase employee motivation so that the goal is to get good work performance.
- g) As a tool to encourage or familiarize superiors (supervisor managers, administrators) to observe the behavior of subordinates.
- h) As a tool to be able to see the weaknesses in the past and improve the ability of future employees.
- i) As a criterion in determining employee selection and placement.
- j) As a tool to identify personal weaknesses and thus can be taken into consideration so that they can be included in additional work training programs.
- k) As a tool to improve/ develop employee skills.
- l) As a basis for improving and developing job descriptions.

Mangkunegara (2013) states that performance indicators include:

- 1) Quality of work is how well an employee does what should be done.
- 2) The quantity of work is how long an employee works in one day. This work quantity can be seen from the work speed of each employee.
- 3) Performing tasks is how far the employee is able to do his job accurately or without mistakes.
- 4) Responsibility for work is an awareness of the obligations of employees to carry out work provided by the company. The results of one's work will provide feedback for the person himself to always be active in doing his job.

2.2 Employee Skills

According to Wahyudi (2002), skills are the expertise to do a job only obtained in practice, these work skills can be grouped into three categories, namely as follows:

- a) Mental skills, such as analysis, making decisions, counting, memorizing.
- b) Physical skills, such as skills related to one's own work.
- c) Social skills, that is, such as being able to influence others, make speeches, offer goods, and others.

Tovey, M. (2001) defines that skills are not only related to one's expertise to do something tangible. Besides physical, the meaning of skill also refers to mental problems, manual, motor, perceptual and even social abilities of a person. The indicators used in this study adapt the theory expressed by Yuniarsih and Suwatno (2008) which are divided into dimensions and indicators as follows

- 1) Proficiency in mastering work,
- 2) Ability to complete work,
- 3) Accuracy in completing work,
- 4) Ability to control yourself,
- 5) Confidence in completing work,
- 6) Commitment to work,
- 7) The ability to train yourself to be better.

2.3 Job Involvement

Job involvement is the mental and emotional involvement of people in group situations that encourage them to contribute to group goals and various responsibilities for attaining those goals. Luthans (2006) defines that job involvement occurs if organizational members place themselves in physical, cognitive, and emotional roles during work.

According to Lodah & Kejner (1965), job involvement is defined as the extent to which a person identifies psychologically with his work or the importance of work in an individual's self-image. An employee is said to be involved in his work if the employee can identify themselves psychologically with his work and considers his performance important for himself, other than for the organization (Prihatini, 2013). Job involvement, as the level of the extent to which a person's work performance, influences their self-esteem and the degree to which a person psychologically identifies himself with his work or the importance of work in his total self-image.

There are several characteristics of employees who have high and low work involvement (Cohen, 2003), including:

A. Characteristics of employees who have high job involvement:

- a) Spend time working,
- b) Have a high concern for work and the company,
- c) Satisfied with his work,
- d) Have a high commitment to careers, professions and organizations,
- e) Give the best efforts for the company.
- f) Absenteeism and turnover intentions are low and highly motivated

B. Characteristics of employees who have low job involvement:

- a) Do not want to try hard for the progress of the company,
- b) Don't care about work or company,
- c) Not satisfied with work,
- d) Do not have a commitment to work or the company,
- e) High absences and turnover intentions,
- f) Having low work motivation,

- g) High resignation rate,
- h) Feel less proud of work and company.

There are three psychological conditions proposed by Luthans (2006) that can increase the likelihood of job involvement in their work. These conditions include:

- 1) Having the meaningful Feeling: feeling the experience that the work being done is useful, and valuable.
- 2) Security: one is able to show or work without fear or have negative consequences on self-image, status, and career.
- 3) Feelings of availability: individuals feel that resources that provide physical, personal, emotional, cognitive sufficiency are available when needed.

According to Robbin and Judge (2008), job involvement has the following indicators:

- a) Attention to work,
- b) Care about work,
- c) Mastering the field of work,
- d) Prioritizing work,
- e) Considering the work as interesting,
- f) Trying bes effortst for the job,
- g) Considering work is important for his pride,
- h) Full of confidence in the job,
- i) Having self-confidence.

2.4 Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction illustrates how a person is motivated towards one's work, people remain happy with their work and having the satisfying feeling towards it, so the work is also designed aiming at increasing employee job satisfaction (Haroon, et al 2012). Job satisfaction indicates that there is a match between a person's expectations that arise with the benefits provided by the work. Job satisfaction or dissatisfaction depends on the difference between what is expected. If the employee gets lower than expected, it will cause the employee to not feel satisfied in doing his work. In addition, emphasis is placed on employers' expectations regarding employee high performance and it is very important to bring to the fore that employee satisfaction is a function of employee performance and the appearance of the company itself (Shen, 2010).

As'ad (1995) mentions factors that influence job satisfaction include:

- 1) Psychological factor is s a factor associated with employee psychiatry which includes interests, job security, attitude towards work and work feeling.
- 2) Physical factors are factors related to the physical work environment and physical conditions of employees, including the type of work, work time management, work equipment, air circulation, and employee health.
- 3) Financial factors are factors related to employee security and welfare, which include payroll systems, social security, and amount of money, facilities provided, promotions and others.

4) Social factors are factors related to social interaction both between fellow employees, with their superiors, as well as employees with different types of work. Brown & Ghiselli (in Sutrisno, 2011) suggested that there are five factors that cause job satisfaction, namely:

- a) Position: humans generally assume that someone who works at a higher job will feel more satisfied than those who work at a lower job. Several studies have shown that this is not always true, but changes in job levels that affect job satisfaction.
- b) Rank: in jobs that base on different levels or classes, the work gives a certain position to the person doing it. If there is an increase in wages, then more or less will be considered a promotion and pride in the new position will change his behavior and feelings.
- c) Financial and social security: it mostly affects job satisfaction.
- d) Quality of supervision: the relationship between employees and the leadership is very important in increasing work productivity. Satisfaction can be increased through attention and good relations from the leadership to subordinates, so that a worker will feel that he is an important part of the work organization.

According to Robbins and Judge (2013), job satisfaction has five dimensions, namely:

- 1) The work itself with indicators: work that matches ability and work that is mentally challenging
- 2) Salary, the indicators include salary and speed of payment.
- 3) Promotion opportunities, indicators include opportunities to advance and ways of selecting promotions.
- 4) Colleagues, indicators include relationships with colleagues and relationships with superiors
- 5) Working conditions which is related to physical environment satisfaction

3. Research Methods

The population in this study was all employees of the Medan City Manpower Office, totaling 62 people comprising of Civil Servants (PNS). Because the population is very limited to fewer than 100 respondents, in this study the authors chose saturated sampling. This study uses data analysis methods, namely path analysis with the help of SPSS software.

The hypotheses that will be tested in this study are:

H1: Work skills have a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

H2: Job involvement has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

H3: Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

H4: Work skills have a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction.

H5: Job involvement has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction.

H6: Work skills have a positive and significant effect on employee performance through job satisfaction.

H7: Job involvement has a positive and significant effect on employee performance through job satisfaction.

4. Research Result

4.1 Substructure Testing I

Based on data processing that has been done, the results of substructure I regression analysis can be seen in the following table:

Table 1: Results of Regression Analysis Substructure I

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	13,908	3,418		4,069	,000
	Work Skills	-,241	,235	,403	2,024	,005
	Job involvement	,738	,270	,543	2,735	,008

a. Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction

Based on Table 1, a regression model for substructure I can be made, namely:

$$Z = 0.403X_1 + 0.543X_2$$

From the equation of the substructure I regression model it can be explained.

- 1) The effect of work skills on job satisfaction is 0.403, which means that if employee work skills increase, job satisfaction will also increase.
- 2) The effect of work involvement on job satisfaction is 0.543, which means that if employee work involvement increases, job satisfaction will also increase.

Based on substructure I regression analysis, it can be explained that:

- 1) Work skill variable has $t_{count} > t_{table}$ that is $2.024 > 2.00$ with a significant value of $0.005 < 0.05$, so it can be concluded that the work skills variable has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction.
- 2) Job involvement variable has $t_{count} > t_{table}$ that is $2.735 > 2.00$ with a significant value of $0.008 < 0.05$. This shows that the work involvement variable has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction.

Table 2 displays the results of the coefficient of determination test for substructure I using the help of SPSS software which shows that the coefficient of determination (Adjusted R Square) is 0.679 or 67.9% which means that the ability of work skills and job involvement in explaining their effects on job satisfaction is equal to 67.9% while the remaining 32.1% is influenced by other variables not examined in this study.

Table 2: Test Results for the Coefficient of Determination Substructure I

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,824 ^a	,679	,688	2,44926
a. Predictors: (Constant), Job Involvement, Work Skills				
b. Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction				

4.2 Substructure Testing II

Based on the data processing that has been done, the results of the substructure II regression analysis can be seen in the following table:

Table 3: Results of Regression Analysis of Substructure II

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	,527	2,542		,263	,896
	Work Skills	,471	,159	,438	4,244	,000
	Job Involvement	,411	,149	,232	2,215	,032
	Job Satisfaction	,264	,134	,273	2,569	,027

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

Based on Table 3, a regression model for substructure II can be made, namely:

$$Y = 0.438X_1 + 0.832X_2 + 0.273Z$$

From the equation of the substructure II regression model it can be explained that:

- 1) The effect of work skills on employee performance is 0.438, which means that if work skills increase by 1 unit, the employee's performance will increase by 0.438.
- 2) The influence of job involvement on employee performance is 0.232, which means that if job involvement goes up by 1 unit, then employee performance will increase by 0.232.
- 3) The effect of job satisfaction on employee performance is 0.273, which means that if job satisfaction increases by 1 unit, then employee performance will increase by 0.273.

Based on substructure II regression analysis, it can be explained that:

- a) Work skill variable has a t_{count} greater than t_{table} that is $4.244 > 2.00$ with a significant value of $0.000 < 0.05$, so it can be concluded that the work skills variable has a significant effect on employee performance, and it can also be seen that the skill variable work has a positive influence on employee performance variables, which shows that if work skills increase, it will be able to increase employee performance, and vice versa, if work skills decrease, it will reduce employee performance.
- b) Job involvement variable has $t_{count} > t_{table}$ that is $2,215 > 2,00$ with significant value $0,032 < 0,05$. This shows that the job involvement variable has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. If job involvement increases, this will

further improve employee performance. Conversely, if job involvement decreases, it will make employee performance declines.

- c) Job satisfaction variable has a $t_{count} > t_{table}$ that is $2.569 > 2.00$ with a significant value of $0.027 < 0.05$. This indicates that the variable job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. If job satisfaction increases, it will further improve employee performance. Conversely, if job satisfaction decreases, it will make employee performance decreases.

Table 4: Substructure Coefficient Determination Test Results II

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,921 ^a	,870	,812	1,578
a. Predictors: (Constant), Job Satisfaction, Work Skills, Job Involvement				
b. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance				

Table 4 displays that the coefficient of determination (Adjusted R Square) of 0.870 or 87%, which means that the influence of the variable work skills, job involvement, and job satisfaction on employee performance is 81.7%, while the remaining 13% can be influenced by others variables that were not examined in this study.

4.3 Path Analysis Test Results

Figure 4.8: Path Diagram

Based on the results of the first and second sub-structural path analysis tests, the path diagram can be drawn, namely:

The structural equation of substructure I is:

$$Z = 0.403X_1 + 0.543X_2$$

The structural equation of substructure II is:

$$Y = 0.438X1 + 0.232X2 + 0.273Z$$

5. Discussion

5.1 Work Skill Has a Positive and Significant Impact on Employee Performance

The results of the study prove that the work skills variable has a positive and significant effect on employee performance variables in Medan City Manpower Office. This means that the higher the employee's work skills can improve employee performance and vice versa if the employee's work skills decrease, the employee's performance will also decrease. From the direct effect that the variable work skills on employee performance gained a significant value of 0.403. This shows that work skills can influence job satisfaction in Medan City Manpower Office. Basically, skills are individual in nature. Each individual will have different levels of skill depending on their abilities and experience. Work skills have great benefits for individuals, companies and society. Skills are also expertise to do a job which is believed to have only obtained in practice (Wahyudi, 2002).

According to Overtoom (2000) employability skills are individual skills and qualities as well as knowledge and attitudes needed in the workplace. Widodo (2015) also added by arguing that training is a series of individual activities systematically increasing expertise and knowledge so as to be able to have professional performance in their field.

Medan City Manpower Office should pay more attention to training facilities for each employee in order to multiply skilled and qualified employees so that they can properly achieve the goals set by the Medan City Manpower Office. Training really has benefits as stated by Rivai and Sagala (2011) that training will help employees in making decisions and solving problems more effectively. Through training and development of achievement, growth, responsibility and progress can be internalized and implemented; increasing job satisfaction and recognition and help employees approach personal goals while improving interaction skills.

Thus, if employees are left unevenly trained, employees will be farther away from the expected abilities, where employees are required to be more skilled in doing work not in accordance with the training needs that employees should receive at least once a year. According to Rohmah (2017) employee skill is one of the factors in efforts to achieve successful organizational achievement. The goal of work skills is to be able to facilitate a job in completing each job effectively and efficiently without any difficulties so as to produce a good employee performance.

The results of this study are consistent with what was done by Sulistiani (2016) which study is on the effect of work ability and work skills on the performance of leasing company employees stating that there is an influence between work skills on employee performance.

5.2 Job Involvement Has a Positive and Significant Impact on Employee Performance

The statistical results that have been discussed in the first sub-structural model in shows that job involvement have a positive and significant effect on employee performance. These results can be proven by statistically significant results of 0.232. From these results it can be seen that the better the work involvement of an employee, the higher the level of performance that can be produced by employees and vice versa, if the job involvement of an employee is unscrupulous then the employee's performance will also decrease. From these results it can be seen that all dimensions of job involvement that is, actively participating in work, showing work as the ultimate, seeing work as important to self-esteem is able to provide value to employee performance.

Employees who work with a high level of involvement will prioritize their work compared to other matters and realize that the work is part of them. With high job involvement will help employees in the process of achievement that every employee wants to achieve, employees who have a good level of involvement will assume that work is a reflection for himself, when employees involve themselves as fully as possible are employees who have a level of awareness that is high and full of responsibility.

In this case high job involvement causes individuals to be more committed to their organizations; conversely low job involvement will make individuals less committed to their organizations for job involvement is an important variable in the lives of many people. High job involvement plays a role in shaping work performance, quality, and quantity of greater work results and high work efficiency.

Job involvement is defined as a measure to which individuals psychologically side with their work and regard the important level of performance achieved as self-esteem (Robbins & Judge, 2008). Job involvement shows how much individual interest in his job or task (Steers & Porter, 2012). It can be concluded that job involvement is the level where a person is involved in his work and considers the work given to him though the most preferred thing to do.

The results of this study are in accordance with that carried out by Gusmarni and Kasmiruddin (2018) entitled the effect of job involvement and Organizational Commitment on employee performance at Milano Teluk Kuantan Mother and Child hospital which also states that job involvement significantly influences employee performance at RSIA Milano Teluk Kuantan.

5.3 Job Satisfaction has a Positive and Significant Impact on Employee Performance

The results of this study prove that job satisfaction variables have a positive and significant effect on employee performance variables. This means that the higher employee job satisfaction can improve employee performance and vice versa, if employee job satisfaction decreases the employee's performance will also decrease. Based on Direct Effect, it can be seen that the effect of job satisfaction on employee performance is 0.273.

Based on the pre-survey of job satisfaction of Medan City Manpower Office, it is known that there are still employees who are indicated to be dissatisfied, especially with the physical work environment. Medan City Manpower Officers stated that the physical

work environment of their workplaces is in under capacity to provide comfort for them, both from the arrangement of the room; the trifling parking lot that the employees had to park their private vehicles beside the highway.

Employees who work with high levels of satisfaction will view their work as a pleasant thing. When employees feel satisfied, employees will be more loyal to the organization, so that discipline, enthusiasm and work morals they have in carrying out their duties and responsibilities will increase. Vice versa, employees with low levels of satisfaction will view their work as mundane work so that in doing their work, the employee will feel forced. If the company has employees whose majority of job satisfaction is low, it will have an impact on the survival of the company.

Job satisfaction refers to the general attitude of employees towards their work (Robbins, 2008: 37). Views or perceptions of individuals who vary in an organizational environment make them feel satisfaction or dissatisfaction with their work. That can affect the attitudes and behavior of individuals in carrying out their duties and functions. An individual's attitude is related to evaluative statements both pleasant and unpleasant. In line with this, as stated by Wexley and Gary (2005: 129) that job satisfaction is a generalization of attitudes toward work based on various aspects of work.

The results of this study are consistent with research conducted by Nur (2013) entitled Conflict, Job Stress and Job Satisfaction which affects the performance of employees at the University of Khairun Ternate which argumentation bases upon that job satisfaction has a positive effect on employee performance meaning the higher the level of job satisfaction will have a positive impact in improving employee performance.

5.4 Work Skill Has a Positive and Significant Impact on Employee Job Satisfaction

The results of statistics on hypothesis testing shows that the variable work skills affect job satisfaction. From these results obtained a significant value of 0,000. From the results of statistical calculations also obtained the value of the beta coefficient of work skills 0.438. These results are positive, which means that when each increase in work skills by 0.438 it will be able to provide an additional job satisfaction of 0.438 units.

Skills are the capacity needed to carry out a number of tasks which are the development of the results of training and experience gained. Skills indicators in this study include: skills, personality and training of Medan City Manpower employees. The term skilled is usually used to describe a person's varying degrees of ability. Skill is the ability to operate work easily and carefully. The term skilled is also interpreted as an act or task, and as an indicator of a level of proficiency. Skills are knowledge that are outwardly present in humans and need to be studied in depth by developing their skills.

Based on observations and interviews conducted by researchers, it can be seen that the level of work skills is very closely related to employee job satisfaction. Employees at the Medan City Manpower Office do not fully have good work skills, there are still many employees who have not been able to separate personal matters from work, followed by employees who are still not confident in doing work because the work currently being charged to these employees is not appropriate with the line of work he was supposed to

run. And there are still employees who state that the employee is placed not in accordance with their abilities. But not all employees are the main factor employees do not have skills. This tends to happen to new employees who join the Medan City Manpower Office. However, employees do not deny that their skills greatly affect their satisfaction at work, but employees really expect enough job training for them to support their work followed by good skills so that they can achieve satisfaction in doing their work.

Based on the above explanation it can be concluded that the work skills of employees affect job satisfaction of employees at the Medan City Manpower Office. The results of this study are consistent with research conducted by Bolung, et al (2018) entitled the influence of professionalism and skills on job satisfaction and their impact on the performance of regional development planning employees in North Sulawesi Province which result states that professionalism and skills have a significant effect on job satisfaction.

5.5 Job involvement has a Positive and Significant Impact on Employee Job Satisfaction

The results of statistical tests also obtained the beta coefficient value of job involvement amounted to 0.232. The result is positive, which means that when each increase in job involvement is 0.232, it will be able to give satisfaction of 0.232 units.

Based on the interview results it can be obtained that some employees have quite low involvement because the work assigned to the employee is not in accordance with the employee's educational background, thus making the employee feel uncomfortable in doing work. Apart from that there are still quite a lot of employees who give priority to personal interests compared to work interests. Thus the work that must be given to employees such as whether a job is routine, requires initiative or requires creativity. With the demands of initiative and creativity in carrying out work, then employees indirectly must be able to spend most of their time, energy, and mind for their work because this is an important part of the individual so that the desires or expectations of the employees are fulfilled. Every employee has the desire to be able to achieve maximum work results in accordance with individual expectations. This expectation will later influence the level of involvement of individual work in carrying out their duties.

Based on the explanation above, it can be concluded that employee job involvement has a positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction. The results of this study are consistent with research conducted by Sanger (2013) with the title appraisal of work performance, job involvement; work motivation on employee job satisfaction in the North Sulawesi High Prosecutor's Office has a simultaneous and partial influence on job satisfaction of North Sulawesi District Attorney's employees. The leadership of the North Sulawesi High Prosecutors Office should pay more attention to the assessment of work performance and job involvement of employees because it has a greater influence on job satisfaction, so it is expected that work productivity can increase.

5.6 Work skill has a Positive and Direct Effect on Employee Performance through Employee Job Satisfaction

The results showed that work skills had a positive and direct effect on employee performance, which means that if employees work skills were good it would have a direct impact on improved employee performance and vice versa if the skills of these employees were poor then this would reduce the level the performance of Medan City Manpower Office employees.

From the results of statistical hypothesis testing that has been done, it is known that the variable of work skills can provide a significant influence on employee performance, because the more skilled an employee is, the better the performance. Statistics show that work skills can directly influence the performance of Medan City Manpower employees.

The results of statistics show that job satisfaction is not able to mediate between work skills with employee performance. This can be seen from the comparison between the direct coefficient beta effect and the indirect effect. The value of the direct effect is 0.438 while the value of the indirect effect is 0.110. From the results of these calculations it can be seen that the direct effect is greater than the indirect effect, so it can be concluded that in this hypothesis job satisfaction is not able to mediate between work skills and employee performance.

Skills are able to provide a direct influence on employee performance in completing tasks and job responsibilities. Everyone's skills must be honed and developed through training or guidance programs. Training must be supported by the basic abilities that the person already has in him. This basic ability can produce something more useful and become an added value for himself or for others when combined with guidance or training. In general, skill is an ability to use reason, ideas, and creativity in doing, making or changing something to be more meaningful so that it can produce an added value from the results of the work performed.

Skills can also be interpreted as an ability and capacity obtained through systematic and ongoing efforts in a smooth and adaptive manner in carrying out complex activities or job functions that involve ideas or cognitive skills, matters or technical skills, and interpersonal skills. Employee skills at the Medan City Manpower Office should be improved in achieving better performance such as having commercial awareness, negotiations and persuasion, which is able to realize company missions through reliable negotiation and persuasion techniques as well as self-confidence which emphasizes the confident attitude rather than superiority. And one also needs to have confidence in his colleagues and company. Supriadi (In Sukidi and Farid, 2016) defines performance as a person's ability in terms of quality and quantity in carrying out their duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to them.

5.7 Job involvement has a Positive and Direct Effect on Employee Performance through Employee Job Satisfaction

The results of statistics show that job satisfaction is not able to mediate between work skills with employee performance. This can be seen from the comparison between the direct coefficient beta effect and the indirect effect. The value of direct influence is 0.232 while the value of indirect influence is 0.148. From the results of these calculations it can be seen that the direct effect is greater than the indirect effect, so it can be concluded that in this hypothesis job satisfaction is not able to mediate between job involvement and employee performance.

Thus, it can be seen that work skills have a strong influence on employee performance at the Medan City Manpower Office. If the employee engages in the work, then the performance will be better for the overall performance of the organization where one works. Therefore, high job involvement will increase organizational commitment as well as employee performance.

Sedarmayanti (2011) revealed that performance is the result of a work of an employee as well as the process of activities involving all members of the organization, where the results of work must be evident, can be measured (compared to established standards) as stated by Jackson and Schuler (2011). And based on the provisions of the implementation of government regulation number 46 in 2011 and the head of the state employment agency number 1 of 2013 concerning performance appraisals to measure performance are divided into two namely: 1). Behavior-based performance (behavior criteria) which focuses on doing work, behavior in doing work based on duties and responsibilities, such as absenteeism, tardiness, carelessness, cooperation, initiative. 2). Performance based on results (result criteria) which focuses on what was completed or produced rather than how the work was completed or produced, such as quantity, quality and time.

6. Conclusions

- 1) Employee work skill has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Medan City Manpower Office.
- 2) Employee job involvement has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Medan City Manpower Office.
- 3) Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on the performance of employees of the Medan City Manpower Office.
- 4) Work skill has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction of Medan City Manpower Department employees.
- 5) Job involvement has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction of Medan City Manpower Department employees.
- 6) Employee job satisfaction is not able to mediate / intervene the influence between work skills variables on employee performance at the Medan City Manpower Office.

- 7) Employee job involvement is not able to mediate / intervene the influence of work skills variables on employee performance at the Medan City Manpower Office.

7. Suggestions

Based on the results of research and discussion, the advice given is as follows:

A. In the future, Medan City Manpower Office should be able to improve the skills and job involvement of employees related to the expertise and awareness of an employee by:

- 1) Making efforts to improve welfare which are intended for the employees to fully focus on carrying out the tasks assigned to them.
- 2) Medan City Manpower Office can strive to be more able to communicate and disseminate the vision, mission, policies, strategies, regulations and organizational values to the employees through coaching, guidance and involvement of employees in the formulation of policies. Thus, it is hoped that employees will increasingly feel they have duties and responsibilities towards Medan City Manpower Office.

B. In the future the Medan City Manpower Office should be able to increase employee job satisfaction related to job promotions, placement that matches employee expertise and employee salaries as well as;

- 1) Medan City Manpower Office conducts socialization related to Republic of Indonesia government regulation No. 13 of 2002 concerning the appointment of Civil Servants in structural positions. the agency must be able to socialize the qualifications (for example, having a rank below the specified level, well-being of both physically and mentally), the specified education level, and to convey all elements of performance appraisal of good value in the last two years transparently.
- 2) Medan City Manpower Officers need to pay attention to employee savings in accordance with the educational background of each employee in preventing employees from feeling bored to do daily work which is a core part of the employee.
- 3) Providing education and training in accordance with each employee's line of work.
- 4) The leadership needs to streamline the supervisory function and provide objective and transparent rewards and punishments to employees so that employees become better at optimizing time in completing work in the future.

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